

Intelligent Navigation Techniques of Autonomous Mobile Robots: A Survey

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Abstract: Navigation is the most essential of autonomous mobile robots that can be highly challenging due to the complexity and level of dynamicity in the tasks and environment. A mobile robot should figure out all feasible paths to navigate safely from a start position to a target position. It should employ strategies such as localization, wall-following, obstacle avoidance, and target-approaching while choosing the best feasible path. Intelligent and knowledge-based systems can aid to find an optimal navigation path. Most review reports focus on a specific category of navigation techniques. Therefore, it is essential to describe strategies and features of the different categories of navigation techniques for autonomous mobile robots in one report. This paper reviews most of the intelligent navigation techniques for mobile robots, then compares these methods and discusses their performance and efficiency in terms of a number of important criteria such as path length and collision rate.

Keywords: Autonomous Robot, Intelligent Navigation, Mobile Robot, Robot Navigation, Path Planning, Obstacle Avoidance.

1. Introduction

Navigation is the fundamental challenge of autonomous mobile robots [8]. The main navigation challenge for autonomous mobile robots is to find an optimal path from a start point to the desired destination in dynamic environments in the presence of static or moving obstacles. If the robot can smoothly navigate from the start position to everywhere in the environment, it will be a milestone to obtain the objective of realizing ubiquitous robotic services in our daily

life. Navigation should cope with challenges such as avoiding obstacles, wall-following, and target-tracking [11, 12]. A mobile robot should navigate toward the target by prioritizing safety, reliability, efficiency, and even social norms [25].

Navigation techniques for autonomous mobile robots can be categorized into two groups: local methods and global methods. The local navigation majorly deals with the obstacle-avoidance. In contrast, global navigation aims at an optimal path toward the target [29]. There are various techniques that can be employed to conduct the navigation of autonomous mobile robots. The traditional navigation methods find the optimal paths for static environments. Nowadays, knowledge-based and intelligent systems (e.g., fuzzy logic [20], deep learning [21, 54], and Bayesian logic [85, 86]) can efficiently manage the navigation process by learning the dynamicity of the environment [13].

Figure 1 illustrates some of the areas that autonomous mobile robots have found applications [14-16]. Foraging is a well-known testing application for multi-robot systems, especially for swarm systems. In the foraging, objects (e.g., pucks and simulated food pellets) are initially distributed across the planar terrain. Then, robots collect and deliver the objects to the pre-defined gathering locations (e.g., nest). In the coverage, robots should investigate all parts of the environment for some purposes such as searching for objects (e.g., landmines) or executing essential actions in the environment (e.g., floor cleaning). The flocking and formation control strategies coordinate the navigation of the mobile robots relative to each other. In the formation of robots, a defined relative position among the robots is established and preserved.

Figure 1. Some applications of mobile robots.

In the box pushing tasks robot(s) are commended to push boxes to the target point along a planned path. Cooperative manipulation is similar to box pushing, except it commands the robots to lift and carry the boxes to the target. Therefore, the robots should synchronize all their actions to successfully execute the pushing/manipulation tasks. In target observation, a team of robots is used to monitor multiple targets. The observation time of the robots should be maximized, i.e., the targets are kept in the view of team members. Coordination of the robots in this application is very sophisticated when the number of targets is more than that of robots. Path planning of multiple mobile robots demands finding an improved path for individual robots among all feasible paths between the start and destination. Robots should cooperate with each other to avoid collisions and deadlocks.

Surveys on autonomous mobile robots navigations [206-209] have mainly been conducted only on a specific category of the navigation techniques. This survey aims to give a perspective on most of the knowledge-based and intelligent navigation techniques. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents navigation techniques. Section 3 evaluates the performance of some of these navigation techniques. Finally, the paper is concluded in Section 4.

2. Autonomous Navigation Techniques

In Figure 2, we present most of the well-known intelligent techniques that are already used in autonomous mobile robots navigation.

Figure 2. Intelligent navigation techniques for mobile robots.

2.1. Human-Aware Techniques

Human-aware navigation techniques are based on human-robot collaborations in a shared environment [23]. Such motion planning technique finds collision-free trajectories for robots in shared environments with human-obstacles and/or human-robot cooperation. Computing a safe robot trajectory in the presence of uncertain human motion is the main challenge.

Althaus et al. [24] have described various features of a robotic platform and task limitations of the robot by using psychological studies on human behaviors. A humanoid system on wheels, namely Robovie, is developed. This robot includes two arms with 4 degrees of freedom for each one, a height of about 120 cm, and a weight of nearly 40 kg. It is designed on a Pioneer platform that has a 45 cm diameter and is a two-wheel differential drive. Five scenarios are utilized to analyze the abilities of the system as (i) the robot enters a room and then looks around for people, (ii) if there are any people in the room then the platform will track them, (iii) the robot stands next to the human(s) and commences or joins a discussion, (iv) the robot leaves the human(s) toward the exit door upon the discussion is over or take some other actions, and (v) the robot restarts some of the predefined plans, reacts to some of the new requests, or walks around the environment in a leisurely or aimless way.

Sisbot et al. [25] have presented a motion planner to perform an explicit action in interaction with human partners. This process is conducted in accordance with the visual field, accessibility, and preferences in terms of relative human-robot placement and motions in the environment. The method considers safety and visibility in hidden zones in the path planner. Figure 3 illustrates the components of this planning method. The system is equipped with a front SICK laser scanner, a tilt and pan camera, infrared proximity sensors & sonars, and three Pentium III processors. It is worth noting HumPos is a module to detect and track human.

Fig. 4. Architecture of a human-aware mobile robot motion planner [25].

Kirby et al. [26] have presented a constraint-optimizing method for person-acceptable navigation. They have addressed limitations of the robot navigation by using human social conventions (e.g., personal space and tending to one side of hallways). These limitations can be considered at the global planning level. This framework can employ an arbitrary number of

social conventions in the planning phase. Furthermore, the authors have conducted some experiments with their framework to evaluate the social behaviors of the robot.

Kruse et al. [27] have presented extensions to the human-aware navigation planners (HANP) in highly dynamic and collaborative conditions. HANP can find more efficient and applicable solutions to robot motion in presence of the humans by using the notion of optimistic planning. Predictive planning aids to predict the movement of a human. The robot can stop in the collision conditions and then follow several plans (e.g., waiting for the human to move) to proceed. The authors have used several cost functions to improve the behavior of the robot when approaching the human. A sigmoid function is used for safety based on the Euclidean distance of a point to a human as follow

$$c_{dist}(dis) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{\cos(\frac{dis}{b} \times \frac{\pi}{2})}{c+dis}\right)^a, & dis < b \\ 0, & else \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where dis is the distance of a point to human, a adjusts the gradient of the function, b is the radius, and c is the inflection circle radius. A sigmoid function is applied for visibility when the robot approaches a static human outside its sight as below

$$c_{vis}(dis, ang) = \begin{cases} \cos\left(\frac{dis}{e} \times \frac{\pi}{2}\right) \times (f + g \times (ang - 45^\circ)), & dis < e \text{ and } ang > 45^\circ \\ 0, & else \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where ang is the absolute angle between xy -orientation of human and vector from human to the point, e limits the radius of function, f adjusts the gradient toward human, and g changes the gradient toward his back. Moreover, another sigmoid function is utilized for prediction in front of a moving human as follow

$$c_{pred}(dis, ang) = \begin{cases} \cos\left(\frac{dis}{e} \times \frac{\pi}{2}\right) \times (f + h \times (180^\circ - ang)), & dis < e \text{ and } ang < 45^\circ \\ 0, & else \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where h adjust the gradient in front of a human.

Foka and Trahanias [28] have studied autonomous robot navigation in dynamic and congested environments by presenting a predictive navigation paradigm. In this paradigm, probabilistic planning and obstacle avoidance are integrated together along with further motion prediction of the humans and/or other obstacles. A hierarchical observable Markov decision process is used to conduct predictive navigation to discover collision-free paths toward the destination. Moreover, the speed of the robot is increased or decreased to apply further motion prediction based on performing the detours. Motion prediction is carried out by long-term

prediction, estimated destination position of a moving object, map of hot points, and motion tracking.

Lam et al. [29] have presented a navigation algorithm that obtains harmonious coexistence between humans and robots via considering their current states. In this algorithm, a robot should not only consider obstacle avoidance and goal-seeking but should also pay attention to interfere with other people or robots. Consequently, the authors have described several harmonious rules by proposing human-centered sensitive navigation in order to guarantee safe and smooth navigation in a human-robot environment. This method considers both humans and robots as sensitive zones in accordance with their security regions or human's psychological conditions. Figure 4 presents this paradigm.

Figure 4. The scheme of the human-centered sensitive navigation [29].

Rios-Martinez et al. [30] have presented a risk-based navigation method that involves both the traditional ideas of the collision risk and the risk disturbance. A robot can participate in a social environment by using this navigation strategy. Torres-Mendez et al. [31] have presented a framework that transfers human-based navigation behaviors to an artificial agent. This framework works based on a spatial conceptual map and can create route directions like those generated by humans. Kruse et al. [32] have evaluated a human-aware global navigation planner in a path crossing condition to improve legibility of the robot navigation behaviors while humans move in the environments. The planning strategy is according to some social costs and static search spaces. Luber et al. [33] have indicated the problem of learning and reproducing the motion behaviors based on walking people for the socially-aware robot motion. The learning is based on observations of humans from large-scale surveillance datasets. Guzzi et al. [34] have developed a fully-distributed algorithm for robot local navigation by using vision-based mechanisms. They have implemented the same heuristic systems for the mutual avoidance applied by humans in presence of sensing uncertainty.

Trautman et al. [35] have studied mobile robot navigation in dense human crowds based on the cooperation of humans with robots and the improvement of navigation performance. They have presented a predictive model of goal-oriented behavior and cooperative collision avoidance. Ramón Vigo [36] has presented a machine learning technique, known as learning by demonstrations. The technique employs an algorithm and a cost function that enables the robot to have not only efficient and safe navigation but also social interaction and awareness for performing high-level tasks. Trautman et al. [37] have explored a basic impediment in classical motion planning for considering a mobile robot through dense human crowds. To achieve the defined goal, the environment exceeds a specific level of dynamic complexity, the planner determines all forward unsafe paths, and the robot freezes in place to avoid the collisions. Obo and Yasuda [172] have presented a fuzzy-based human-aware navigation framework for mobile robotic systems. Li et al. [173] have developed a reinforcement learning-based human-aware navigation mechanism in indoor environments. As deep reinforcement learning has obtained great success in human-aware navigation policies, this algorithm has improved the navigation process of mobile robots. A dynamic local goal setting technique and a map-based safe action space are used to navigate the robot.

2.2. Neural Network

Artificial neural networks are used to solve complex signal processing or pattern recognition problems. In information systems, a neural network is a system of connected units (or nodes) called synthetic neurons. A network usually consists of layers where each layer has built upon one or more than one neuron. The first layer receives raw input and the last layer generates the output of the system. Figure 5 illustrates the layer structure of a simple neural network [38].

Figure 5. A schematic of neural network.

Na and Oh [39] have developed a hybrid control architecture that consists of behavior-based reactive navigation and model-based environment classification. Initially, a neural network is designed by 16 prototypes of the topological maps based on local navigation environments. Then, a reactive behavior controller is trained based on neural networks in order to learn human steering commands for all the 16 prototype environments. Afterward, a modified potential field method is presented to choose a specific reactive behavior according to the free space vector. Wang et al. [40] have presented a modular navigation controller for mobile robots that works based on spiking neural networks. This controller is a behavior-based target-approaching navigation technique that consists of three components: an obstacle-avoidance, a wall-following, and a goal-approaching. It is more appropriate to the unstructured and unknown environments that do not need accurate mathematical modeling. Figure 6 shows this scheme.

Figure 6. Block diagram of a target-approaching navigation controller based on spiking neural networks [40].

Ran et al. [41] have developed a convolutional neural network-based robot navigation technique that purely operates based on un-calibrated spherical images. Path prediction is applied to simplify orientation estimation and the navigation problem is decomposed into a series of classification tasks to improve computational performance. Ko et al. [42] have verified the effects of neural network-based autonomous navigation in homecare mobile robots. They have evaluated recurrent neural networks in comparison with a multi-layer perceptron neuron in the navigation process of an autonomous mobile robot. Chen et al. [43] have studied the significance of the memory-based neural networks in perception-action loops for autonomous robot

navigation. They have provided some of the essential tools to generalize the unpredicted scenarios according to the supervised and quantitative features.

Zhu et al. [174] have presented a planner based on a recurrent fuzzy neural network to conduct the trajectory and motion of mobile robots for the target approaching and obstacle avoidance issues. The planner takes the advantage of the learning capability of neural networks and the inference capability of fuzzy logic. Singh and Thongam [175] have introduced a method based on an artificial neural network to generate a collision-free near-optimal path for a mobile robot to tackle the moving and stationary obstacles. The entire workspace is partitioned into five equal segments. A collision-free segment is selected and the speed of the robot is adjusted by a multilayer perceptron neural network.

2.3. Fuzzy Logic

Fuzzy logic is a knowledge-based decision-making system that can solve complex problems. The fuzzy inference system is composed of four units: fuzzification, rule base, inference engine, and defuzzification. Fuzzy logic is used for mobile robot navigation [20, 44].

Aguirre and González [45] have presented the design, coordination, and fusion of elementary fuzzy behaviors for mobile robot navigation. The design is conducted by regulatory control and fuzzy logic control. The coordination is applied using a fuzzy system to define the applicability of every behavior. The fusion fuses the preferences of every behavior in the experimental process. Seraji and Howard [46] have presented behavior-based navigation on terrain via a fuzzy system and a measure of terrain traversability. Roughness, slope, and discontinuity are three terrain features that this method takes into account in the navigation.

Wang and Liu [47] have provided a real-time robot navigation approach in unknown environments with dead ends based on fuzzy systems. This approach is composed of a grid-based map model and a behavior-based navigation method. The grid-based map model stores not only environmental information but also overall information of the robot. In contrast, the behavior-based navigation method discusses the local minimum problem that is indicated by a goal-oriented robot navigating in unknown indoor environments. Huq et al. [48] have offered a technique to select different motor schemas autonomously by using a fuzzy context-dependent system of robot behaviors. This technique consists of the strategic and reactive type schemas to facilitate operations of the local and global motion planning. The Voronoi vertices are treated as immediate objectives for the local planning and a safe path is initially generated based on a Voronoi diagram for the global planning.

Pradhan et al. [49] have investigated navigation techniques for mobile robots in unknown environments by using fuzzy decision making. Each mobile robot is equipped with an array of ultrasonic sensors to determine the distances of the obstacles around it. Besides, it is equipped with

an infrared sensor to detect the bearing of the target position. A fuzzy controller navigates the robot throughout the environment. Motlagh et al. [50] have described a control technique for reactive navigation of the mobile robots based on an expert fuzzy cognitive map. They have attempted to solve two critical problems: a large number of rules and an inefficient definition of contributing factors. The control values are derived by the causal inference mechanism of the fuzzy cognitive map based on motion concepts and causal interactions. This control system is applied to control a Pioneer platform. Figure 7 depicts a block diagram of the developed system.

Figure 7. The fuzzy logic controller for robot motion control [50].

Ibrahim et al. [51] have used a fuzzy logic controller for autonomous navigation of a dynamical hexapod robot. The controller takes into account the constraints of the line and wall-following. Hossen et al. [52] have represented a hybrid fuzzy controller for real-time navigation of a mobile robot using multiple sensors. This controller is built by the automatic generation of the membership functions via a minimal number of fuzzy rules based on a hybrid fuzzy clustering algorithm. It is improved by the least square method and gradient descent algorithm in order to have a better performance with a minimal set of rules.

Abiyev et al. [53] have studied navigation problems of mobile robots in densely cluttered with obstacles uncertain environments. A type-2 fuzzy system is presented to navigate a mobile robot. The input fuzzy parameters are the current angle and distance signals, while the output fuzzy parameter is the turn angle of the robot. Nadour et al. [176] have designed a visual navigation system for mobile robots in indoor environments based on fuzzy logic and an optical flow approach. This system consists of two Takagi-Sugeno fuzzy-based controllers, which

conduct obstacle avoidance and goal-seeking by image/video processing. The first fuzzy controller uses the optical flow values that are determined by the Horn-Schunck algorithm for the detection and prediction of the obstacle positions. The second one is applied to aid the robot to navigate toward the target position.

Mohanta and Keshari [177] have presented a knowledge-based fuzzy system with a probabilistic roadmap for target seeking and path planning of the mobile robots in two folds. The first fold discovers the shortest path between source and destination in a cluttered environment. The probabilistic roadmap method is applied to specify a straight-lined path by connecting intermediate nodes on the navigation path. In addition, the second fold generates the smoothen curves throughout the navigation path with sharp corners. The fuzzy system adjusts a suitable heading angle to conduct smooth turns. Patle et al [178] have presented a path-planning algorithm that consists of a probability method and fuzzy system. The probability method is used to navigate the mobile robot while the fuzzy system is applied to grade the obstacles existing on the navigation path. The primary function for navigation of the mobile robot toward the target point is fuzzy grading similar to the probabilistic decision. The secondary function is defined as a path-planning scenario, which is applied by the probability distribution function.

2.4. Deep Learning

Deep learning trains representations of the data with multiple levels of abstraction using computational models and multiple processing layers. It discovers the intricate structure in large data sets based on the back-propagation algorithm [54]. Various domains such as speech recognition, object recognition, and drug discovery can be efficiently handled by deep learning. Chen et al. [55] have presented a deep learning method for autonomous navigation of mobile robots. This method uses a convolutional neural network to recognize ambient scenes and identify some of the useful information (e.g., location of the doors).

Tai and Liu [56] have categorized robotic control problems as a deep data-driven sensory-motor system, deep reinforcement learning, and deep model-predictive control. Deep data-driven sensory-motor system maps the raw sensor inputs to control the defined commands or create the notion on the pair-wise sensor-control information. Deep reinforcement learning trains a representation of the policy learning models, which are grouped into value-based and policy-optimization methods. In the deep model-predictive control, sensory data can be not only obtained and identified by human supervision but also created by simulation and the trained models. Ribeiro et al. [57] have presented a pedestrian detector for robot navigation based on real-time deep learning. This method is used to solve the human-aware robot navigation problem. The pedestrian detector consists of the aggregating channel features and a deep convolutional neural network in order to provide an accurate and fast response.

Beyer et al. [58] have introduced a deep learning-based object detector that operates with 2-dimensional (2-D) range data. Laser scanners generate accurate 2-D range data and cover a large field of viewpoints to make interesting sensory data for the robot. The hand-crafted features and boosted classifiers indicate potential research on detection ways in laser 2-D range data. Kahn et al. [179] have presented a generalized computation graph that works based on the value-based model-free and model-based methods. The main feature of this method is to instantiate the interpolating between model-based and model-free. The navigation model is learned based on the obtained raw images to work in the complex indoor environments including a few hours of fully autonomous and self-supervised training.

Gordón et al. [180] have presented autonomous navigation for mobile robots that are composed of deep learning techniques and the Single Shot Detector algorithm. This method provides a robustness feature in terms of speed and precision to conduct detection of the persons and objects on the navigation path.

Chiang et al. [181] have used a method to learn an end-to-end point-to-point process and a path-following navigation behavior for collision-avoidance with moving obstacles. The noisy lidar observation is the input and the robot linear and angular velocities are outputs of the system. The method is trained in small and static environments in order to discover a deep reinforcement learning reward and neural network architecture. Firstly, the algorithm figures out a reward to maximize task completion. Afterward, it discovers a neural network architecture to maximize the cumulative of found reward.

2.5. Neuro-Fuzzy System

Neuro-fuzzy systems are formed by the combination of fuzzy logic and neural network. Neuro-fuzzy navigation has been considered in the literature [59]. Figure 8 demonstrates an adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system known as the first-order Takagi-Sugeno fuzzy model. It is supposed that the model includes two inputs and one output and five layers. Every node i in the first layer is an adaptive node with the membership function of a fuzzy set A ($=A_1, A_2, B_1, \text{ or } B_2$) as follows

$$O_{1,i} = \mu_{A_i}(x) \quad \forall i = \{1, 2\} \quad (4)$$

$$O_{1,i} = \mu_{B_{i-2}}(y) \quad \forall i = \{3, 4\} \quad (5)$$

where k_1 (or k_2) is input of node i and A_i (or B_{i-2}) is a linguistic value (e.g., “small”). Membership of A using the triangular membership function can be determined as below

$$\mu_A(x) = \max \left[\min \left\{ \frac{x-a_i}{b_i-a_i}, \frac{c_i-x}{c_i-b_i} \right\}, 0 \right] \quad (6)$$

where $\{a_i, b_i, c_i\}$ specifies the parameter set. Every node in the second layer is a fixed node that is labeled by Π . It is calculated by the product of all the incoming signals as follow

$$O_{2,i} = w_i = \mu_{A_i}(x)\mu_{B_i}(y) \quad \forall i = \{1, 2\} \quad (7)$$

The output of every node indicates the firing strength of a rule by a fuzzy AND operator. Any node in the third layer is a fixed node that is labeled by N. Every node i calculates a ratio of the rule i 's firing strength to the sum of firing strengths of all the rules as below

$$O_{3,i} = \bar{w}_i = \frac{w_i}{w_1 + w_2} \quad \forall i = \{1, 2\} \quad (8)$$

The output of this layer is the normalized firing strengths. Any node i in the fourth layer is an adaptive node as follow

$$O_{4,i} = \bar{w}_i f_i = \bar{w}_i (p_i x + q_i y + r_i) \quad \forall i = \{1, 2\} \quad (9)$$

where \bar{w}_i indicates the normalized firing strength from the third layer and $\{p_i, q_i, r_i\}$ is the parameter set of the node. Finally, single node of the fifth layer is a fixed node that is labeled by Σ . Crisp value of this node can be calculated as below

$$f = O_{5,1} = \sum_i \bar{w}_i f_i = \frac{\sum_i w_i f_i}{\sum_i w_i} \quad \forall i = \{1, 2\} \quad (10)$$

Figure 8. Architecture of an adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system [63].

Rusu et al. [60] have discussed a neuro-fuzzy system for sensor-based navigation of mobile robots in indoor environments. The control unit applies a top-bottom hierarchy of various tasks and behaviors to conduct robot navigation. The mobile robot utilizes infrared and contact sensors to detect target points and avoid collisions. Zhu and Yang [61] have presented a neuro-fuzzy based method for target seeking and obstacle avoidance. A learning algorithm adjusts parameters of the membership functions of the fuzzy system based on neural network techniques and

another learning algorithm is presented to suppress extra rules of the rule base. Furthermore, the “dead cycle” problem is solved by a state memory strategy.

Mohanty and Parhi [62] have presented a technique that is composed of a fuzzy inference system and artificial neural network to address autonomous mobile robot navigation. An adaptive fuzzy controller is developed by a single Takagi-Sugeno fuzzy system that has four input parameters (i.e., front obstacle distance, left obstacle distance, right obstacle distance, and heading angle) and one output parameter (i.e., velocity). Al-Mayyahi et al. [63] have used two fuzzy controllers to regulate both of the left and right angular velocities for achieving the target position and two fuzzy controllers to adjust an optimal heading for avoiding the obstacles. Moreover, two velocity controllers apply the sensed data of three sensor inputs (i.e., front distance, right distance, and left distance) to conduct the low-level motion control. Table 1 represents some of the training data that are used in this controller.

Table 1. Samples of the training data in the adaptive neuro-fuzzy navigation in [63]

No.	Inputs			Outputs	
	Front distance	Right distance	Left distance	Right angular velocity	Left angular velocity
1	0.100	0.100	0.100	-40	-40
2	0.800	0.339	0.800	67.999	43.999
3	0.4873	0.309	0.800	61.997	25.992
4	0.4269	0.219	0.800	43.997	-28.008
5	0.786	0.800	0.303	22.230	60.743

Mohanty and Parhi [64] have presented a sensor-based technique for autonomous mobile robot navigation in uncertain environments. The inputs are fed by various obstacle range data (i.e., front obstacle distance, left obstacle distance, right obstacle distance, and heading angle) from the ultrasonic sensors and the output is the steering angle of the robot. Baturone et al. [65] have described low-cost embedded controllers to manage robot navigation based on a small number of fuzzy rules and neuro-fuzzy techniques. Takagi-Sugeno fuzzy model is used in the fuzzy inference engine and fuzzy sets are generated by the normalized triangular functions. Heuristic and fuzzy knowledge are aggregated together by fuzzy rules. Cherroun and Boumehraz [66] have presented a soft computing navigation approach for an autonomous mobile robot. This approach utilizes an intelligent control system for path following behavior of the mobile robots based on a neuro-fuzzy controller.

Fouladvand et al. [67] have introduced an efficient neuro-evolutionary algorithm for robot navigation in partially visible environments. This algorithm includes three neural networks to improve the efficiency of learning. In presence of an obstacle, a fuzzy obstacle avoidance controller takes over the control of the robot. Table 2 represents the comparison results of this

method. It demonstrates that the performance of the robot is improved by a fuzzy algorithm because of having fast response.

Table 2. Robot efficiency with or without a fuzzy-based obstacle avoidance system [67]

Run	Objective function	
	With fuzzy-based obstacle avoidance	Without fuzzy-based obstacle avoidance
0	1.2	1.4
100	0.9	1.2
200	0.75	1
300	0.55	0.7
400	0.38	0.6
500	0.15	0.5
600	0.07	0.43
700	0.8	0.4
800	0.7	0.38
900	0.7	0.2

Mohanty and Parhi [68] have presented an intelligent motion planning method based on fusions of different sensor-extracted information to determine the steering angle of a robot. Pothal and Parhi [69] have described a navigation controller for the single and multiple mobile robots in highly cluttered environments based on an adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system (ANFIS). It enables the robot to conduct essential behaviors such as obstacle avoidance, target seeking, and speed controlling. Al-Jarrah et al. [70] have presented a coordination and path planning approach for multiple mobile robots based on neuro-fuzzy and fuzzy probabilistic to navigate a multi-robot team from the start position toward the target avoiding fatal collisions. Each robot is equipped with a low-level probabilistic fuzzy controller to remove stochastic uncertainties.

Al-Dabooni and Wunsch [71] have applied value-gradient learning to track the reference trajectory of a nonholonomic mobile robot under uncertain conditions. This method calculates optimal values of the left and right torque using a first-order Sugeno fuzzy neural network to navigate mobile robots with high performance. Rao et al. [72] have developed a navigation technique for an autonomous mobile robot by implementing obstacle avoidance and target-seeking behaviors. The navigation is controlled by a fuzzy system, neural network, adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system, and safe boundary algorithm. The inputs of the controller are fed by the sensors that are placed on the front, left, and right sides. The output determines the angular velocity of the robot. Figure 9 illustrates a schematic of the navigation strategy and fuzzy controller that are used in this navigation method.

Adarsh and Ramachandran [182] have designed a data fusion algorithm using an adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system for mobile robot navigation. The fusion algorithm is employed within the controller of the robot combines inputs from the ultrasonic and infrared sensors to obtain a better environment perception. Pandey et al. [183] have designed and implemented a sensor-actuator control technique for the navigation of mobile robots. This technique is

developed by multiple adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference systems for two-dimensional environments in presence of the stationary and moving obstacles. Three infrared range sensors are installed on the front, left, and right sides of the robot to detect the obstacles. The inputs of this controller are fed by sensory data to calculate a suitable speed value for both right and left motors. It was assumed that the speed of the robot is at least more than or equal to the speed of the moving obstacles and goals.

Figure 9. Navigation of nonholonomic mobile robot by using neuro-fuzzy logic and safe boundary algorithm [72]. (a) Navigation strategy; (b) A schematic of fuzzy controller.

2.6. Ant/Artificial Bee Colony and Fuzzy Logic

The ant colony is a biological optimization algorithm that finds an optimal path by imitating the behavior of ants searching for food. A combination of ant colony algorithm and fuzzy logic can enhance the performance of the robot navigation in most cases [73]. Garcia et al. [74] have presented a solution for path planning in mobile robots based on ant colony optimization. The decision-making procedure is determined based on the distance between a source node and the target node, and ants can remember the visited intermediate nodes. A fuzzy inference system is applied to select an optimal path using a simple tuning algorithm. Juang and

Hsu [75] have addressed a reinforcement ant-optimized fuzzy controller. The inputs are fed by sonar sensors and the output is the steering angle of the robot. Purian and Sadeghian [76] have described an approach to solving mobile robot navigation in dynamic environments in accordance with the heuristic features of an optimized ant colony algorithm. A fuzzy system is applied to choose optimal paths between the source and target points. It is worth noting ant colony algorithm optimizes parameters of the fuzzy rules.

Lizarraga et al. [77] have described a methodology for the design of an optimized fuzzy logic controller for autonomous mobile robots with the aid of ant colony optimization. This method uses a systematic and hierarchical optimization by the modification of the conventional ant colony algorithm and ant partition. Castillo et al. [78] have explored a dynamic fuzzy controller and an ant colony optimization for diversity control in mobile robot navigation. The main objective of this work is to avoid the full convergence with a dynamic variation of a particular parameter.

Li et al. [79] have presented a navigation control for mobile robots based on behavior manager, toward-goal behavior, and wall-following behavior. The wall-following control is performed by a recurrent fuzzy cerebellar model articulation controller and an improved dynamic artificial bee colony. Figure 10 shows the workflow of this method. In the initialization phase, every bee indicates a solution that is randomly initialized from the solution space. In the fitness evaluation phase, the fitness value of every bee is determined subsequently. The employed bees look for any new food sources and acquire a random search in their neighborhood. Afterward, onlooker bees select a new food source regarding the probability value that is related to the fitness value of the employed bee.

Tutuko et al. [184] have presented a combination of ant colony optimization and fuzzy logic to select an optimal path. They showd that their navigation technique takes the advantage of both fuzzy logic for unpredictable and uncertain environments and simplicity of ant colony for discovering optimal solutions. Juang et al. [185] have presented a rule-based cooperative framework to conduct a multi-objective evolutionary fuzzy system for robot navigation. A multi-objective rule-based ant-colony optimization is used to tune the parameters in the fuzzy system. An additional colony is generated to store all the fuzzy rules to increase the optimization rate of the algorithm.

Figure 10. Flowchart of the improved dynamic artificial bee colony [79].

2.7. A-Star Algorithm

The A-star algorithm is a heuristic search algorithm that finds the shortest path between two points. It consists of a function $g(x)$ to maintain the traveled cost and a function $h(x)$ to determine the cost between current point and target point as below

$$f(n) = h(n) + g(n) \quad (11)$$

where $h(n)$ is heuristic distance and $g(n)$ is actual distance from the nodes that are passed by the algorithm [80].

Loong et al. [81] have presented a path-following mobile robot with intelligent path mapping and an A-star algorithm. They have used a microcontroller-equipped wheeled mobile

robot in the evaluation process. A computer application is developed to map the optimal paths from the start location toward the goal by using the A-star algorithm and a series of instructions. Dianjun [82] has developed an indoor mobile-robot path planner. This method considers the fundamental features of mobile-robot technology for indoor localization into structured environments. The path is initially planned by the A-star algorithm that contains all of the planning point coordinates. This method calculates inflection point, rotation direction, and minimal rotation angles.

ElHalawany et al. [83] have evaluated an A-star path-planning algorithm to find out the most optimal path for mobile robot navigation. Input data is obtained by a grid-based map that is achieved in accordance with a vision-based obstacle detection system. This algorithm uses the size of the robot as an essential parameter to choose the safest path for the navigation process and avoid sharp turns. Duchoň et al. [84] have studied path planning of a mobile robot based on a grid map, reliable reactive navigation, and simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM). They have introduced several modifications and improvements to the A-star algorithm. The evaluation results focus on computational time and path optimality.

Kusuma and Machbub [186] have used the A-star algorithm to find the best path according to coordinates of the robot and targeted object. They have applied the intermediate points, namely waypoints, to navigate the robot from the current position to the next position until it arrives at the target position. If the robot misses the target objects or moves away from the assigned waypoints, another path will be selected again. The authors have used the Manhattan, Euclidean, and Diagonal heuristic functions. The Manhattan distance heuristic can be determined as follow

$$h(n) = |x_a - x_b| + |y_a - y_b| \quad (12)$$

where (x_a, y_a) is the coordinate of the current position and (x_b, y_b) is the coordinate of the target. The Euclidean distance heuristic can be calculated as

$$h(n) = \sqrt{(x_a - x_b)^2 + (y_a - y_b)^2} \quad (13)$$

The Diagonal distance heuristic can be specified as follow

$$h(n) = |x_a - x_b| + |y_a - y_b| + (\sqrt{2} - 2)\min(|x_a - x_b|, |y_a - y_b|) \quad (14)$$

2.8. Bayesian logic

Bayesian logic integrates decision-making with inferential statistics to develop a probability inference that can use the knowledge of prior events to predict future events [85, 86]. Bayes' theorem gives the likelihood of an event occurring in future trials given the frequencies in prior trials as:

$$P(A|B) = \frac{P(B|A)P(A)}{P(B)}, P(B) \neq 0 \quad (15)$$

where $P(A|B)$ is the likelihood of event A occurring given that B is true and vice versa for $P(B|A)$.

Censi et al. [87] have introduced a Bayesian framework for optimal motion planning in environments with uncertainty. The time and covariance of poses in the path-planning stage were minimized. Diard and Bessiere [88] have presented a Bayesian map formalism to model the interactions between a robot and its environment. The map is built based on a particular probability distribution to deal with the uncertainties. Vasudevan and Siegwart [89] have introduced a conceptualization and classification of space based on the Bayesian approach. The objects in the space are used to create concepts and classify the places via the Naive Bayes Classifier.

Martinez-Cantin et al. [90] have presented an online path-planning method that uses a Bayesian optimization mechanism to trade off the exploration and exploitation dynamically. Budiharto et al. [91] have presented a geometrical model and a maneuvering method aggregated together with the Bayesian approach to control obstacle avoidance based on the state estimation. Vladareanu et al. [92] have improved the navigation process of the walking robots in non-stationary and non-structured environments. A Bayesian approach is used for the dynamical stability control of motion on rough terrain areas. Ko et al. [93] have developed the Bayesian model of an egocentric semantic map that is composed of spatial node relationships and spatial object relationships. The robot can predict its location by Bayesian filtering that consists of leverages spatial relationships among observed objects. Moreover, it can perceive navigable space with a Kinect sensor to move toward the target point while preserving the reference head direction.

Souza et al. [94] have addressed an active perception and a technique to model the roughness of a terrain robot, incrementally. This approach can look for waypoints to reduce overall vibration during the travel path. It uses Gaussian processes and Bayesian optimization for decision-making procedures. Conti et al. [95] have characterized a navigation framework that unifies measurements from multiple sensor technologies such as UWB, ZigBee, and inertial sensors.

Okal and Arras [96] have discussed learning the socially normative robot navigation behaviors based on Bayesian inverse reinforcement learning. They have used a flexible, graph-based representation to capture relevant task structure on navigation paths. Richter et al. [97] have developed a planner for high-speed navigation in unknown environments with a Bayesian learning mechanism. It predicts the feasibility and cost of trajectories. Hence, mobile robots can estimate future events beyond map frontiers for fast navigation.

Jadaliha et al. [187] have developed fully Bayesian prediction algorithms for mobile robotic sensors using Gaussian Markov random fields. The sum of time-varying mean function and Gaussian Markov random field is applied to make a model of the Spatio-temporal field of interest with unknown hyper-parameters. The exact Bayesian solution to the computing problem of the predictive field inference is derived under uncertain hyper-parameters, uncertain localization, and measurement noise. Bourne et al. [188] have presented a nonparametric Bayesian-based planning algorithm for autonomous plume source term estimation and source seeking. This algorithm is developed for mobile robots that are equipped with gas concentration sensors. The robots use a Gaussian-plume likelihood model via a Bayesian-based process and simultaneously look for and move toward the source by using the model-based source seeking methods (e.g., biased-random-walk).

2.9. Evolutionary Algorithms

An evolutionary algorithm consists of various heuristic techniques to solve optimization tasks based on some features of natural evolution such as mutation and selection. An evolutionary algorithm is able to evolve optimality-based solutions over time through mutation and crossover for a complicated problem with constraints [98]. Figure 11 shows the main elements of an evolutionary algorithm.

Figure 11. Flowchart of an evolutionary algorithm [98].

Vadakkepat et al. [99] have presented a methodology for real-time path planning of the robots by evolutionary techniques. They derive optimal potential field functions with the aid of genetic algorithms. This method can navigate mobile robots that are situated among moving obstacles with various fitness functions such as goal-factor, smoothness-factor, and obstacle-factor. Mata et al. [100] have addressed a deformable model of the real-time color vision system to conduct mobile robot navigation. This model automatically discovers and trains the information obtained from each object by using the genetic algorithm, neural networks, and perception module. Fernandez-Leon et al. [101] have discussed scaling up the complex behaviors in evolutionary robotics. Every behavior is applied by a controller based on an artificial neural network or neuro-controller. Moreover, a hierarchy of the neuro-controllers is utilized to resort to the paradigm of the layered evolution in the navigation process. Kim and Kim [102] have explained a multi-objective, quantum-inspired evolutionary algorithm to design an efficient fuzzy-based path planner for mobile robots. This algorithm uses a probabilistic mechanism and the techniques of quantum computing.

Herrera Ortiz et al. [103] have presented a multi-objective evolutionary algorithm to specify optimal parameters of an artificial potential field for mobile robot navigation. They have attempted to minimize distance toward the goal point, maximize the distance between the robot and the nearest obstacle, and maximize the distance traveled on each field configuration. Capi et al. [104] have evaluated the effects of the three neural networks on controlling the robot to achieve a target point in urban dynamic environments. The robot navigates from the start position to goal position into an environment with moving obstacles based on an evolutionary approach, GPS, and compass sensor. da Silva Assis et al. [105] have described an evolutionary algorithm to control the sensors and motors of the robot for navigation. Chen et al. [106] have expressed an evolutionary algorithm to address the fact that pedestrians cannot cross walls during the walking process. They have established a walking motion model by using the extended Kalman filter, step size, and azimuth change.

Lee et al. [107] have presented an online multi-objective evolutionary method for navigation of the humanoid robots with a significant reduction in computation costs while maintaining the robustness and scalability features for the robot navigation. The approach is based on successively online solving a series of small multi-objective problems with the local information of robot walking. Figure 12 illustrates block diagram of this method for humanoid robots.

Figure 12. Flowchart of the online navigation of humanoid robots [107].

Uyeh et al. [189] have formulated the greenhouse layout optimization problem in protected systems to discover the most appropriate points on each bed for creating an access path. This process can lead to total traveling time from all points in the greenhouse to the base point being reduced considerably. The differential evolution of an evolutionary algorithm is used to solve the optimization problem that included the standard bed feature, area of the greenhouse, beginning and final points for navigation, and the space required for inter-bed and rotary robot navigation. Orozco-Rosas et al. [190] have solved the path-planning problem of mobile robots by using a membrane evolutionary artificial potential field. This approach discovers the parameters for creating a feasible and safe path by using a combination of membrane computing with a genetic algorithm and artificial potential field. The path length is minimized by the delimited compartments in which multisets of the parameters are properly used based on rules of the biochemical inspiration.

2.10. Genetic Algorithm

The genetic algorithm can solve both constrained and unconstrained optimization problems through the natural selection process and biological evolution. It works based on the repeated modifications of a population associated with individual solutions. The algorithm selects some of

the high ranked individuals from the current population in each step to produce the next-generation [108].

Whitbrook et al. [109] have described a method to transfer a set of behavior developed on a specific robotic platform (e.g., Epuck) to another robotic platform (e.g., Pioneer). A genetic sequence-based on the artificial evolution of behaviors in Epuck is obtained and employed to seed an idiotypic, artificial immune system on the Pioneers. Shi and Cui [110] have presented a dynamic path-planning scheme with a genetic algorithm. The algorithm uses a coding technique to convert the two-dimensional path data to one-dimensional data and includes a fitness function, and specific genetic operators to accelerate the convergence. Yun et al. [111] have addressed an optimal path-planning mechanism for mobile robots based on the improved genetic algorithms. The initial population is generated by using an obstacle avoidance algorithm and a distinguish algorithm. Path planning of mobile robots is determined by domain heuristic knowledge through the crossover, mutation, refinement, and deletion operators.

Kang et al. [112] have presented a solution based on the genetic algorithm to dead-end problems of robot navigation. They have applied two mechanisms including a dead-end detection mechanism and a genetic algorithm via an online training mechanism. The robot uses the generation of the best chromosome and online training for enabling the robot to escape from the dead-end area. Tsai et al. [113] have presented a parallel elite genetic algorithm for the global path planning of autonomous mobile robots in structured environments. This method takes advantage of the better population diversity, inhibits the premature convergence, and keeps parallelism in comparison with the conventional genetic algorithm. These procedures are used to select a near-optimal, collision-free, continuous path. Tuncer and Yildirim [114] have addressed a mutation operator of the genetic algorithm for the path-planning problem of mobile robots in dynamic environments. This method can find an optimal path by taking advantage of a strong optimization ability. It is worth noting this mutation operator avoids premature convergence to improve the navigation process.

Samadi and Othman [115] have presented a global path-planning method with a genetic algorithm. A genetic-based optimization selects an appropriate path based on the length and cost of the possible paths according to hexagonal grid map modeling. Shiltagh and Jalal [116] have developed a modified genetic algorithm for global path planning that analyzes the map of the working environment by a grid model to choose an optimal collision-free path. Lee and Kim [117] have explained an effective initialization method for genetic-based path planning. Their method surpasses the existing navigation methods by improving the initialization process.

Findi et al. [118] have presented a genetic network programming technique with reinforcement learning based on predicting the collision positions of robot navigation in dynamic environments. This technique offers safe navigation with effective obstacle avoidance and reduces the latency time of the obstacle avoidance process. The fitness function of the genetic algorithm is calculated as follow

$$fitness = \frac{\varpi}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{C_3 r_t}{e^{r(\Delta\theta)^2 + (v-v_{max})^2}} \quad (15)$$

where N is the total number of the trials, M is the number of the steps required for obstacle avoidance, $r(\Delta\theta)$ is the rate of steering angle change between two consecutive steps $\Delta\theta$, v is velocity of the Mobile Robot (MR), and v_{max} is maximum velocity of the MR. Here, ϖ is a factor for balancing the movement of MR in both directions which is determined as below

$$\varpi = (\eta_{total} - |\eta_{right} - \eta_{left}|) / \eta_{total} \quad (16)$$

where η_{total} , η_{right} , and η_{left} indicate total turning actions, the number of turnings to right, and the number of turning to left during the obstacle avoidance, respectively. Moreover, C_3 is specified as follow

$$C_3 = \begin{cases} 0, & d(MR, O_i) \leq d_c \\ 5, & else \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

where d is the radius of a virtual circle surrounded each obstacle, O_i is the nearest obstacle, and d_c is the radius of a virtual circle surrounded each obstacle.

Patle et al. [194] have presented a Matrix-binary Codes based Genetic Algorithm (MGA) that uses the matrix-trace-based mechanism to sequence the operation during the navigation and GA looks for the best collision-free fit path. dos Santos and Goncalves [195] have offered a navigation system to enable a sailboat for arriving at any target point in the environment. This system is composed of a short-term path planner and a low-level heading controller against the wind. The satisfactory upwind paths are discovered by using a genetic-based optimization approach.

2.11. Genetic-Fuzzy System

Both genetic algorithms and fuzzy logic are potential systems that can find optimal solutions for most decision-making problems. Therefore, their integration as the genetic-fuzzy system can operate better than a system with only one approach. Pratihari et al. [119] have presented a genetic-fuzzy approach to solve motion planning problems of the mobile robots in presence of the moving obstacles. The genetic algorithm adjusts the scaling factors of state variables and the rule sets of a fuzzy controller in the navigation among the moving obstacles. This approach optimizes the traveling time of an off-line robot by selecting the optimal fuzzy rules and optimal scaling factors. Martinez et al. [120] have explained a tracking controller for the dynamic model of the unicycle mobile robots. They have integrated genetic algorithms with the kinematic and torque controllers based on the type-2 fuzzy system.

Wu et al. [121] have provided a fuzzy controller in accordance with a genetic-based control system for robot navigation in pipe environments. The genetic system optimizes the fuzzy

controller by the modification of membership functions and the commands assigned to a pipeline robot. Begum et al. [122] have used the integration of fuzzy logic and genetic algorithm to solve the simultaneous localization and mapping problem of mobile robots. The fuzzy system applies an island model genetic algorithm for the search process from among a potential region of the pose space. Martínez et al. [123] have applied the integration of a kinematic-torque-based type-2 fuzzy controller and genetic algorithms for tracking control of a unicycle mobile robot.

Senthilkumar and Bharadwaj [124] have presented a hybrid genetic-fuzzy system for autonomous mobile robots that improves the fuzzy rules that control the obstacle avoidance actions and behaviors in navigation. In the genetic unit, genes appear in the form of distances and angles labels. Besides, chromosomes are represented as a rule written in Boolean algebraic form. Figure 13 shows the main units and strategies of the fuzzy controller and genetic algorithm in the hybrid genetic-fuzzy system.

Figure 13. Schematic of the hybrid genetic-fuzzy system [124].

Benbouabdallah and Qi-dan [125] have presented a target-tracking controller for mobile robots by using a fuzzy system in a way that a genetic algorithm improves the scaling factors of this fuzzy system with the aim of enhancing the smoothness of the robot trajectory. Zhao et al. [126] have proposed a fuzzy controller in order to efficiently guide a mobile robot along a

collision-free path toward the target position in the unknown multi-obstacle environments. A genetic algorithm improves membership functions and the rule base of the fuzzy controller.

Bakdi et al. [127] have addressed the path planning of mobile robots based on genetic algorithms and adaptive fuzzy-logic control. They have analyzed the initial results of the two-Kinect cameras system that are installed on a two-wheeled indoor mobile robot. The genetic algorithm creates a collision-free optimal path to make a relation between the start position and the target position. Moreover, sensor fusion predicts the current position and orientation of the robot by the Kalman filter. Rath et al. [196] have presented a fuzzy and a genetic controller for path planning of a humanoid robot in a cluttered environment. The inputs of the fuzzy controller are fed by sensor outputs based on the nearest obstacle distances and bearing angle of the robot to calculate the first turning angle. Afterward, the inputs of the genetic-based controller are fed by the first turning angle derived from the fuzzy controller along with other inputs to calculate the second turning angle as the final output.

2.12. Learning Systems

Learning techniques such as machine learning, active learning, and deep learning are used for the navigation of autonomous mobile robots. Learning is a general technique that can be independently applied to navigate the robots from the start position to the target position.

Wellington and Stentz [128] have proposed an adaptive learning method that focuses on the loop around vehicle predictions, unlike the traditional methods that determine the terrain the vehicle is currently traversing. Features are obtained based on range points of the forward-looking sensors through a locally weighted learning module. Chen et al. [129] have presented multi-category classifiers with parameters optimized via swarm optimization in wall-following robot navigation. Classification-based learning in the training phase of the particle swarm achieves high performance with a significant saving on training time.

Kostavelis and Gasteratos [130] have introduced a two-layer navigation scheme for indoor environments. In this scheme, the low layer uses a 3D SLAM system and an RGB-D sensor while the high layer applies a content-based representation algorithm. The authors have utilized a learning procedure based on a support vector machine to recognize multiple dissimilar places. Matuszek et al. [131] have discussed the problem of parsing natural language commands and control structures in robot execution systems. In this system, the example pairs of English commands and the corresponding control language expressions are employed to learn a parser.

Vasquez et al. [132] have evaluated inverse reinforcement learning algorithms for robot navigation techniques in crowds. They have indicated that inverse reinforcement learning makes optimal models of the factors for people's actions. Bacciu et al. [133] have used adaptive planning to context-aware mobile robot navigation. They have applied the integration of a

model-based planner and a distributed learning system in accordance with reservoir computing. This method utilizes personalized planning and resource allocations to obtain user preferences and environmental changes.

Baleia et al. [134] have presented an approach for online learning of robot navigation based on correlated haptic and depth cues. By using this approach, the robot can incrementally learn the traversable features of the objects. Moreover, the robot can form a mapping between descriptors of the objects that are obtained by sensors and stiffness of the objects. Hafez and Loo [135] have presented a topological Q-learning algorithm that uses a topological ordering mechanism among observed states of the environments. This algorithm can incrementally build an environmental map based on the Instantaneous Topological Map model. Learning techniques accelerate updates of the value function. Figure 14 depicts the architecture of this system.

Figure 14. Architecture of the topological Q-learning agent [135].

Altuntaş et al. [136] have considered mobile robot navigation by using reinforcement learning algorithms. The mobile robot can move toward a given target point using an obstacle avoidance strategy that includes a high success rate in both simulated and real environments. Kretzschmar et al. [137] have created a model of the cooperative navigation behavior of humans. They have conducted this model based on a mixture distribution to capture both discrete navigation decisions (e.g., going left) and natural variance of the human trajectories. The model can imitate the behavior of the pedestrians and replicate certain behaviors in the goal environments of the robot. Zhu et al. [138] have addressed target-driven visual navigation in indoor environments with deep reinforcement learning. They have applied an actor-critic model to operate as a function of the goal for enabling the best generalization. This system offers a

scene having high-quality 3D scenes and a physics engine to allow agents for interacting with objects via actions.

Li et al. [197] have presented a role-playing learning scheme for mobile robot navigation in populated environments. A systematic simulative reinforcement learning environment is constructed with the pedestrians' trajectories and maps that are collected from a number of real-world crowd data sets. Kim et al. [198] have focused on two critical problems for autonomous robot navigation in dynamic environments; prediction of the pedestrian motion and control of the robot with the prediction for safe navigation. A pedestrian is predicted by using a kernel matrix that is applied in Gaussian process regression with the learning low-rank structured matrix to find an orthogonal basis. Safe navigation of the robot is conducted by using the structured kernel subspace learning.

2.13. Machine Learning

Machine learning includes intelligent techniques that receive input data and by doing some statistical analyses predict the outputs in a range of given values. Machine learning algorithms are categorized into three groups: supervised machine learning, unsupervised machine learning, and reinforcement learning [22]. Procopio et al. [139] have addressed learning terrain segmentation with classifier ensembles to autonomous robot navigation in unstructured environments. Machine learning methods are used to train models with a near-field terrain appearance and stereo readings for near-to-far learning to predict far-field terrain.

Casarrubias-Vargas et al. [140] have used machine learning algorithms to improve simultaneous localization and mapping of robot navigation. They have applied an extended Kalman filter and visual information to achieve the optimal results. Furthermore, specific visual landmarks of the environments are obtained by the Viola and Jones techniques. Choi et al. [141] have described a control method for mobile robot navigation by using machine learning algorithms and camera vision. This method uses image processing and feature selection steps to define the state of the robot from raw images using a neural network and supervised learning. Kostavelis et al. [142] have presented a machine learning technique for traversability classification of the terrain. A depth map of the scene is provided by the stereo vision and suitable features of the scene are developed by a V-disparity image calculation. Figure 15 illustrates the flow chart of this navigation technique.

Fig. 16. Workflow of the supervised traversability learning for robot navigation [142].

Goil et al. [143] have presented a machine learning method for collaborative control of an assistive semi-autonomous wheelchair. This algorithm uses statistical machine learning to learn task variability with demonstration examples. It is developed in the context of the shared-control powered wheelchairs to provide assistance to individuals in challengeable driving scenarios (e.g., doorway navigation). Giusti et al. [144] have addressed a machine learning technique to the visual perception of the forest trails for mobile robots. They have studied problems of perceiving forest or mountain trails by using a single monocular image in accordance with a robot traveling on the trail. This technique applies a deep neural network and a supervised image classifier.

Mo et al. [145] have used a combination of computer vision and machine learning to solve problems of the robot indoor navigation. This method conducts navigation of an autonomous robot by imitation of the experts' behaviors. It uses prior experiences of the robot navigation to learn a control strategy by an imitation learning algorithm. Geng et al. [146] have considered a joint learning problem of the perception and control characteristics by a reinforcement learning framework. In order to solve this problem, they have presented an effective architecture using reinforcement extreme learning machine. It is worth noting the reward function is designed to give a reward to the mobile robot based on outcomes of the navigation process.

Zhou et al. [199] have presented a vision-based navigation system for robotic systems that works based on creating the place and head-direction cells by learning from images, generating the topological maps by the learned cell representations, and conducting the navigation process by hierarchical reinforcement learning. Wang et al. [200] have developed a biological-based cognition mechanism for mobile robot navigation in unknown environments. The mechanism uses the motivated developmental network to mimic the supervised learning of the cerebellum and the reinforcement learning based on the radial basis function neural network to simulate the reward-based learning of the basal ganglia and integrates them together to construct a hybrid complex cognition model.

2.14. Radio-Frequency Identification (RFID)

An RFID system is composed of two parts: tag and reader. RFID uses radio frequencies to read the information that is stored on the tag attached to an object [147-149].

Kulyukin et al. [150] have described the application of the RFID systems in robot-assisted indoor navigation for the visually impaired in the presence and absence of visually unpaired participants. This method navigates the robot at moderate walking speeds and prevents oscillation in narrow spaces. Gueaieb and Miah [151] have presented an RFID-based intelligent technique for mobile robot navigation in unknown environments without vision and an approximate map of the robot workspace. Milella et al. [152] have evaluated the effects of low-cost and passive RFID tags on the development of mobile security systems. Initially, a fuzzy inference system is used to localize RFID tags in a geometric-based environment. Then, a robot navigated in an indoor environment by using the RFID and a laser rangefinder.

Park and Hashimoto [153] have presented a passive RFID based technique for localization and pose estimation of mobile robots that uses only passive RFID tags to predict the location and orientation of the robots. Kim and Chong [154] have conducted navigation of the mobile robots by direction sensing RFID reader. This scheme triangulates the location of the transponder with the direction of the arrival estimates. Luimula et al. [155] have discussed RFID-augmented environments and user interfaces for efficient remote navigation with a mobile robot in such environments.

Hossain et al. [156] have presented a navigation approach for autonomous mobile robots with passive RFID systems. This approach has less complexity in the navigation strategy and predicts both position and orientation of the autonomous robots. Besides, a polar coordinate system is utilized on the navigation surface of the robot based on constant displacements. Arulselvi et al. [157] have presented a navigation method for indoor mobile robots with RFID and ultrasonic sensors. The robot can automatically move along hallways based on the scanned range data until a tag refers to the topological map for the next movement mission. Tatsukawa et al. [158] have used passive RFID systems to navigate mobile robots while avoiding collisions with walls and obstacles. A passive RFID tag with obstacles is installed. Consequently, mobile robots are able to avoid obstacles based on the information stored on tags.

Khaliq and Saffiotti [159] have addressed a stigmergic method for goal-directed navigation by RFID systems. A full-scale robotic system can navigate on the RFID floor in a real apartment. The essential information is stored on the floor so that it can be applied by a mid-size robot or a larger domestic robot. Khaliq et al. [160] have applied stigmergy and RFID technology to control point-to-point safe navigation of a mobile robot. Moreover, they keep a certain safe distance from any planned critical locations.

Wu et al. [201] have presented a robot localization approach that combines RFID with laser data. Firstly, a model is used for RFID antenna angle probability with a fuzzy reasoning algorithm when the robot detects an RFID tag. Afterward, the Bayes rule is applied to predict the direction of the robot. Finally, the global localization of the robot is determined by the fusion of the laser ranging data.

3. Evaluation Analysis

This section evaluates navigation techniques for autonomous mobile robots under different simulation conditions. Table 3 represents an overall evaluation of all the categories in terms of the knowledge base, inference engine, learning, and intelligence. These results indicate that fuzzy logic, neuro-fuzzy system, ant colony, and fuzzy logic, Bayesian logic, evolutionary algorithm, genetic algorithm, and genetic-fuzzy system include all of the essential features for efficient navigation. Moreover, human-aware techniques, neural networks, deep learning, learning systems, machine learning, and RFID hold learning and intelligence features. However, the A-star algorithm uses only the learning feature to select the shortest path between two desired positions.

Table 3. An overall evaluation of the navigation techniques for mobile robots

Category	Features			
	Knowledge base	Inference engine	Learning	Intelligence
Human-aware techniques	×	×	√	√
Neural network	×	×	√	√
Fuzzy logic	√	√	√	√
Deep learning	×	×	√	√
Neuro-fuzzy system	√	√	√	√
Ant colony and fuzzy logic	√	√	√	√
A-star algorithm	×	×	√	×
Bayesian logic	√	√	√	√
Evolutionary algorithm	√	√	√	√
Genetic algorithm	√	√	√	√
Genetic-fuzzy system	√	√	√	√
Learning systems	×	×	√	√
Machine learning	×	×	√	√
RFID	×	×	√	√

Table 4 represents the overall performance of the probabilistic autonomous robot navigation in which the robot moves in dynamic environments with human motion prediction. The evaluation results are carried out for five dynamic environments with and without motion prediction. These approaches demonstrate better simulation/experimental results when the prediction of the human movement is employed with. Furthermore, the performance with and

without including human motion prediction varies more when the number of humans in the environment increases. In other words, including human motion prediction while the number of humans is big cause improving the navigation performance considerably.

Table 4. Performance evaluation of the probabilistic autonomous robot navigation in dynamic environments with human motion prediction [31]

Experiment type	The number of humans	With prediction	Without prediction	The number of human areas
<i>dyn1</i>	1	0.947	0.938	1
<i>dyn2</i>	2	0.922	0.873	1
<i>dyn3</i>	3	0.859	0.786	1
<i>dyn4</i>	4	0.795	0.691	1 or 2
<i>dyn4</i>	4	0.823	0.584	1
<i>dyn4</i>	4	0.767	0.798	2
<i>dyn5</i>	5	0.788	0.609	1 or 2
<i>dyn5</i>	5	0.818	0.590	1
<i>dyn5</i>	5	0.758	0.628	2

Table 5 contains the comparison results of the fuzzy-probabilistic roadmap (Fuzzy-PRM) method with a probabilistic roadmap (PRM). The results indicate that the processing time and path length of the Fuzzy-PRM controller is less than those of the PRM controller for all the experiments. Therefore, the Fuzzy-PRM controller has high efficiency compared to the PRM controller. It is worth noting the improved values demonstrate that the performance of the Fuzzy-PRM controller is noticeable.

Table 5. Evaluation results of the fuzzy-probabilistic roadmap and probabilistic roadmap [177]

Experiment No.	PRM controller		Fuzzy-PRM controller		Improvement (%)	
	Processing time (sec)	Path length (pixel)	Processing time (sec)	Path length (pixel)	Processing time (sec)	Path length (pixel)
1	11.5	956	10.6	883	7.826	7.635
2	11.7	972	10.9	910	6.837	6.378
3	11.9	988	11.1	921	6.722	6.781
4	30.2	2516	28.6	2386	5.298	5.166

Table 6 shows the evaluation results of the duality technique of probability and fuzzy logic based navigation [178] in simulations and experiments. The comparisons are carried out based on path length and navigation time under four different scenarios. The results indicate that path length and navigation time in the probability-fuzzy logic method are shorter than that in the fuzzy logic, genetic algorithm, and artificial neural network methods. Evaluation results in the second scenario represent that performance of all the methods in Robot-2 is better than that in Robot-1. Consequently, the efficiency of the methods can be ordered as follow

Probability-fuzzy logic > Artificial neural network > Genetic algorithm > Fuzzy logic

Table 6. Simulation and experimental results of the probability-fuzzy logic method [178]

Scenario type	Method	Simulation		Experiment		
		Path length (cm)	Navigation time (sec)	Path length (cm)	Navigation time (sec)	
Single robot in a static environment	Fuzzy logic	157.15	29.21	170.55	32.74	
	Genetic algorithm	156.40	27.64	167.7	29.50	
	Artificial neural network	155.52	25.30	164.52	27.82	
	Probability-fuzzy logic	154.19	23.45	160.89	24.77	
Multiple robots in a static environment	Fuzzy logic	Robot-1	223.89	39.93	238.99	44.57
		Robot-2	182	34.53	194.90	38.31
	Genetic algorithm	Robot-1	220.95	36.20	233.95	39.89
		Robot-2	180.69	32.98	191.89	35.10
	Artificial neural network	Robot-1	219.68	33.64	230.78	35.4
		Robot-2	179.82	29.83	190.52	32.33
	Probability-fuzzy logic	Robot-1	218.74	32	227.04	33.65
		Robot-2	179	28	186.6	29.39
Presence of moving obstacle	Fuzzy logic	321.17	45.00	-	-	
	Genetic algorithm	316.95	42.20	-	-	
	Artificial neural network	312.47	38.36	-	-	
	Probability-fuzzy logic	310.74	36.65	-	-	
Moving goal situations	Fuzzy logic	366.23	53.14	-	-	
	Genetic algorithm	359.73	48.30	-	-	
	Artificial neural network	354.16	45.05	-	-	
	Probability-fuzzy logic	350	43	-	-	

Table 7 represents the evaluation results of the navigation techniques for multiple mobile robots in highly clutter terrains using an adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system [69]. These results are separately carried out for five different cases under two scenarios and are analyzed in terms of path length and running time for simulations and experiments. Comparing the results demonstrate that the average error between simulations and experiments (which is approximately 10%) is tolerable for all the cases. Besides, the path lengths and running times indicate that this method can properly handle the navigation of the robot(s).

Table 7. Comparison results of mobile robot navigation in highly clutter terrains using adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system [69]

Scenario type	Type	Path length (pixel)			Time taken (sec)		
		Simulation result	Experimental result	Percentage error	Simulation result	Experimental result	Percentage error
Single robot	Case 1	25.7645	28.6300	10.09	16.38	18.30	10.49
	Case 2	25.5346	28.4300	13.24	16.16	18.00	10.22
	Case 3	25.1376	27.8500	12.87	16.29	18.20	10.49
	Case 4	25.7835	28.7500	10.32	16.40	18.30	10.38
	Case 5	25.9467	28.7600	09.78	15.92	17.80	10.56
Four robots	Case 1	23.6487	26.5400	12.22	15.84	17.70	10.51
	Case 2	23.8635	26.4300	11.71	15.76	17.60	10.45
	Case 3	23.8456	26.8600	11.22	15.92	17.80	10.56

	Case 4	23.6598	26.1800	12.95	15.80	17.60	10.23
	Case 5	23.8456	26.9500	11.52	15.61	17.50	10.80

Table 8 evaluates simulation results of the fuzzy logic, neural network, and adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system in mobile robot navigation. The results indicate that compared to the other methods, in most cases, adaptive neuro-fuzzy has the highest efficiency because of the shortest time the robot requires to arrive at the target position. Moreover, fuzzy logic has the lowest efficiency compared to the neural networks and adaptive neuro-fuzzy due to the longer arrival time.

Table 8. Comparison results of fuzzy logic, neural network, and adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system in mobile robot navigation [72]

Environment No.	Arrival time (s)		
	Fuzzy logic	Neural network	adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system
1	43	42	39
2	39	38	36
3	41	39	34
4	45	43	40

Figure 16 illustrates comparison results of the recurrent fuzzy cerebellar model articulation controller [79], compared to the artificial bee colony [161], particle swarm optimization [162], quantum-behaved particle swarm optimization [163], differential evolution [164], and the adaptive differential evolution with optional external archive [165] methods. These navigation results are conducted for each method under four different cases. The results indicate that the fuzzy cerebellar model, in most cases, needs the lowest time to navigate the mobile robots to the target position.

Figure 16. Comparison results of multiple robot navigation techniques [79].

As described in the previous section, Duchoň et al. [84] have presented a path planning method for a mobile robot by using a modified A-star algorithm. The authors have evaluated the performance of the A-star [166], Basic Theta* [167], Phi* [168], and JPS (A-star) [169] methods that use the A-start algorithm or its modified form. As described in Table 9, evaluations indicate that JPS (A-star) has the lowest computational time in all the scenarios. Therefore, this algorithm is the best one in the aspect of computational time compared to the other algorithms. In contrast, the shortest path in all the scenarios was achieved by Basic Theta* which is able to examine the navigation path for every angle.

Table 9. Performance evaluation of mobile robot navigation techniques based on A-star algorithm [84]

Algorithm	Scenario 1		Scenario 2		Scenario 3	
	Computational time (ms)	Path length (cells)	Computational time (ms)	Path length (cells)	Computational time (ms)	Path length (cells)
A-star	229	499,3625	353	601,8011	447	595,2670
Basic Theta*	998	477,3128	2347	580,0478	3518	581,9875
Phi*	1019	477,5218	2898	582,6714	4473	584,1820
JPS (A-star)	21	499,3625	30	605,3158	34	595,2670

Table 10 represents the evaluation results of the evolutionary algorithms to find the shortest path toward the target position in autonomous mobile robot navigation. These evaluation results are carried out for the best statistics under different environmental conditions. As seen in the results, the membrane evolutionary artificial potential field finds the shortest path in comparison with the other evolutionary algorithms. This method combines the genetic algorithm

and artificial potential field via a membrane structure employing merger and divider operators. These features empower data communications among individuals to provide feasible and efficient paths. The efficiency of these algorithms can be ordered as below

Membrane evolutionary artificial potential field > Bacterial potential field > Pseudo-bacterial potential field > Parallel evolutionary artificial potential field

Table 10. Comparison results of the evolutionary algorithms for mobile robot navigation [190]

Environment	Path length (m)			
	Parallel evolutionary artificial potential field	Pseudo-bacterial potential field	Bacterial potential field	Membrane evolutionary artificial potential field
M01	5.7839	5.6461	5.6033	5.4600
M02	9.1234	8.8565	8.8253	8.5558
M03	9.4492	9.2910	9.2325	8.9352
M04	10.0683	10.0133	9.7815	9.3122
M05	6.7931	6.5934	6.5721	6.3761
M06	13.4315	13.1992	13.2194	11.1761
M07	8.1361	8.0234	7.9446	7.7252
M08	8.9660	9.0150	8.7588	8.2837
M09	7.3781	7.2646	7.1973	6.9588
M10	4.9546	4.8519	4.8103	4.6746
M11	8.9952	8.7750	8.6808	8.4388
M12	9.8120	9.6016	9.5519	9.2406

Table 11 describes the comparison results of the genetic network programming with reinforcement learning [118], the obstacle target correlation-based Q-learning [170], and artificial potential field [171] methods. The comparisons are conducted in terms of hit rate and miss rate under various environments. The evaluation results show that, in most experiments, the highest hit rate is achieved by the genetic network while the lowest hit rate is obtained by artificial potential field. In addition, the genetic network has the lowest miss rate for all the environments. These results demonstrate that the efficiency of the genetic network method is very considerable to avoid the obstacles on the navigation path.

Table 11. Comparison results of the robot navigation based on genetic network, Q-learning, and artificial potential field methods [118]

Experiment No.	Hit rate			Miss rate (%)		
	Genetic network programming with reinforcement learning	Obstacle target correlation based Q-learning	Artificial potential field	Genetic network programming with reinforcement learning	Obstacle target correlation based Q-learning	Artificial potential field
1	187	178	167	6.6	11	16.8
2	185	179	176	7.5	10.8	12

3	187	182	170	6.5	9	15
4	185	174	176	7.7	10.5	12
5	186	183	168	7	8.8	16
6	187	172	173	6	11.5	11
7	185	175	168	7.6	12.7	16
8	186	184	180	7.1	8	10
9	186	176	172	7	12	14
10	183	182	177	8.5	9	11

Table 12 contains evaluation results of the structured kernel subspace learning method for mobile robot navigation in terms of average collision rate (ACR) and minimum distance (MinD) in comparison with Gaussian process motion controller, vector field histogram, autoregressive vector field histogram, and reactive planner. The ACR parameter is calculated for each scenario based on the 30 independent trials. The results demonstrate that structured kernel subspace learning gives the best performance with 20% basis vectors while the Gaussian process motion controller has the collision rate higher than the previous method. Moreover, the collision rate of autoregressive vector field histogram is reduced compared to vector field histogram as it employs a prediction of the future positions of moving obstacles. All the methods, except vector field histogram, obtain similar minimum distances to obstacles. In most cases, the vector field histogram shows the lowest performance among all the methods.

Table 12. Comparison results of the learning techniques for robot navigation [198]

Scenario	Parameter	Structured kernel subspace learning			Gaussian process motion controller	Vector field histogram	Autoregressive vector field histogram	Reactive planner
		Rank ratio (10%)	Rank ratio (20%)	Rank ratio (40%)				
1 object	ACR (%)	0	0	0	3.33	6.67	3.33	0
	MinD (mm)	1969	1839	1708	1761	1539	1824	1988
2 object	ACR (%)	6.67	3.33	3.33	5.0	15.0	13.33	10.0
	MinD (mm)	1422	1400	1300	1344	1165	1523	1506
3 object	ACR (%)	6.67	6.67	8.89	8.89	14.44	13.33	8.89
	MinD (mm)	1062	1228	1254	1218	930.2	1087	1116
4 object	ACR (%)	6.67	8.83	8.83	8.83	17.5	11.67	10.0
	MinD (mm)	839.4	951.7	1083	1144	804	855	1100
5 object	ACR (%)	11.33	8.67	12.0	8.0	18.67	12.0	15.33
	MinD (mm)	836.2	785.9	1022	861	684.9	721.4	809.4
5 object	ACR (%)	16.67	12.78	9.44	12.78	22.22	13.33	15.0
	MinD (mm)	928.9	757.7	1008	783.8	602	749.9	784.5
Average	ACR (%)	8.01	6.63	7.00	7.72	15.75	11.16	9.87
	MinD (mm)	1126.3	1160.4	1229.2	1185.3	954.2	1126.7	1217.3

The simulation and comparison results indicate that intelligent navigation techniques show the highest performance in comparison with the traditional navigation methods. These results are carried out under a number of simulation/experimental scenarios to find the optimal path from

the start position to the target position while minimizing important parameters such as path length, navigation time, and collision rate.

4. Conclusions

This paper discussed the main objectives, strategies, and evaluation results of the most intelligent navigation techniques for autonomous mobile robots. First, various applications of mobile robots including foraging and coverage, flocking and formations, box pushing and cooperative manipulation, multi-target observation, and multi-robot path planning were discussed with emphasis on robot navigation in dynamic environments. Afterward, the paper described most of the intelligent techniques for the navigation of autonomous mobile robots. These techniques are categorized into 14 groups: human-aware techniques, neural network, fuzzy logic, deep learning, neuro-fuzzy system, ant colony and fuzzy logic, A-star algorithm, Bayesian logic, evolutionary algorithm, genetic algorithm, genetic-fuzzy system, learning systems, machine learning, and RFID. Most categorizes use artificial intelligence algorithms (e.g., neuro-fuzzy) for efficient navigation and some others use a combination with traditional methods (e.g., radio-frequency identification).

Some of the techniques were compared to each other in terms of processing time, path length, navigation time, hit rate, miss rate, average collision rate, and minimum distance. The results demonstrated the techniques that use a combination of intelligent algorithms have higher performance and are more efficient. Obstacle avoidance and localization, which are the main challenges in mobile robot navigation, and applications of software systems in robot navigation will separately be focused on in future works.

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